

FWF Data Management Plan (DMP) CONNECT V1.0 (02/2026)

I General Information	
I.1 Administrative information	<p>PI: Prof. Andrea Siebenhofer-Kroitzsch, Andrea.siebenhofer@medunigraz.at Grant-DOI: 10.55776/CSP1965525 DMP version: 1.0</p>
I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources	<p>Data management responsibility: Christina Radl-Karimi, Christina.radl-karimi@medunigraz.at</p> <p>All data management responsibilities rest with the project team at the Medical University of Graz, and all work packages will be carried out by the project's personnel. The time required for data management tasks is covered by the project's personnel resources and integrated into the respective work packages. Secure storage, backup, and long-term preservation are provided by the Medical University's IT infrastructure, resulting in no additional hardware or storage costs. No repository charges are expected, as raw data will not be publicly shared due to ethical and data protection considerations.</p> <p>Scientific abstract:</p> <p>Project start: 1 April 2026</p> <p>Wider Research Context: The CONNECT project is an extension to the ongoing A+CHIS project (FWF project number FG11), which aims to tailor evidence-based health information (EBHI) to individual information needs. This is vital for informed decision-making and positive health behaviour. However, effectively communicating EBHI while maintaining scientific accuracy remains challenging. Citizens often struggle to recognize and evaluate the trustworthiness of health information. This project addresses this challenge through a Citizen Science approach.</p> <p>Objectives: The objective is to co-create guiding principles to connect what citizens value in health information with established evidence-based quality criteria. Specifically, we aim to explore the public's criteria for trustworthy health information and combine them with scientific criteria, resulting in co-created guiding principles for effectively communicating the significance of EBHI to the public. These principles will assist A+CHIS researchers and relevant stakeholders to communicating EBHI more effectively, making it easier to identify trustworthy sources.</p> <p>Methods: We will employ a collaborative Citizen Science approach. The project involves work packages for project management, Citizen Scientist (CS) recruitment, exploration of public criteria for trustworthy health information, development guiding principles, and process evaluation. CSs will engage in qualitative data collection and interpretation, culminating in the co-creation of guiding principles during a two-day workshop. Various data validation approaches will be used, alongside a tailored communication plan, to ensure meaningful CS involvement throughout the project.</p> <p>Level of Innovation: The co-created guiding principles for communicating EBHI will enhance the patient-relevant execution of the A+CHIS project. Collaborating with CSs is an innovative and effective strategy to mitigate "research waste". Our long-term vision is to establish a standing Citizen Scientist advisory group at our Institute. The CSs in this group will contribute to our Institute's research strategies, study designs, and dissemination of results.</p>

	<p>Role of Researchers Involved: Prof. A. Siebenhofer-Kroitzsch (PI), a leading member of the A+CHIS project, brings expertise in health services research and invaluable links to other Citizen Science environments. In CONNECT, she serves as the principal investigator. <u>C. Radl-Karimi, PhD</u> specializes in qualitative data methodologies, and her prior experience with participatory concepts such as co-creation and co-production forms the basis for this Citizen Science project. She will oversee recruitment and project coordination. She will be supported by <u>N. Berger</u>, a Research Scientist at IAMEV, who has a background in psychology and public health. <u>Dr. N. Posch</u> specializes in health literacy and the promotion of EBHI. In CONNECT, she introduces CSs to the MAPPinfo checklist for assessing EBHI.</p>
II Data Characteristics	
<p>II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data</p>	<p><u>How will new data be collected, generated or reused?</u></p> <p>The project will generate qualitative data within a Citizen Science framework, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sociodemographic data of Citizen Scientists (CSs) (e.g. age range, gender, social background) collected during recruitment • Self-documented reflections on health information materials (print, digital, and video formats) • Audio recordings and transcripts of semi-structured interviews • Qualitative analysis data (e.g. coded transcripts and thematic summaries) • Documentation from co-creation workshops (e.g. workshop notes, draft versions of guiding principles) • Process evaluation data (feedback from CSs and researchers collected before, during and after) • Project management documentation (e.g. meeting protocols and internal project documentation) <p>No external data will be reused.</p> <p><u>What data (types, formats, and volumes) will be collected or produced?</u></p> <p>Data formats include text documents (DOCX, PDF), audio files (WAV/MP3), MAXQDA project files, and tabular files (XLSX/CSV). Where conversion to open formats is not possible, original formats are stored. The total data volume is expected to remain below 50 GB.</p>
III Documentation and Data Quality	
<p>III.1 Metadata and documentation</p>	<p><u>What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?</u></p> <p>Standardized data collection protocols for CS reflections (WP2), a semi-structured interview guide in lay language (WP2), and standardized meeting protocols for each CS meeting (WP2 and WP3) will be used.</p> <p>Consistent file naming, including date stamps, and structured folder organization will ensure traceability.</p> <p>Qualitative data will be documented within MAXQDA, linking raw data, codes (codebook) and analytical outputs.</p> <p><u>What metadata standards will be used?</u></p> <p>The Dublin Core (DCMI) standard will be applied. Metadata will be tracked in an Excel file, including: project title, creator, date of data collection, work package, description, contributors (CSs), data type (audio, transcript, workshop), format (MP3, DOCX, MAXQDA), and file name.</p> <p>Consistency and quality will be ensured through standardized data collection protocols and the semi-structured interview guide. CSs will receive training in data collection and interview techniques and can pre-test the interview process. Researchers will review collected data, and transcripts will be checked</p>

	<p>against audio recordings. Qualitative analysis will follow a transparent coding framework, with findings discussed and validated through team meetings and member checking.</p> <p><u>Guidance for folder and file naming conventions (to be expanded as needed):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - File names should be concise and not exceed max. 64 characters. - Only uppercase letters, lowercase letters, and numbers are permitted. - The underscore (_) will be used as an element delimiter. - Literature files (e.g., articles, reports) should follow this format: FamilyName_Year_AbbreviatedTitleWithCapitalLetters Example: Smith_2022_PrinciplesOfCitizenScience - Dates must follow the order Year-Month-Day (e.g., YYYYMMDD) - The names of project members who comment on documents should be added at the end of the file name using their initials (e.g., CRK). - For version control, a dedicated folder for previous versions (VV – Vorversionen) will be created to store older files.
III.2 Data quality control	<p><u>How will data consistency and quality be ensured?</u> Consistency and quality will be ensured through standardized data collection protocols and the semi-structured interview guide. CSs will receive training in data collection and interview techniques and can pre-test the interview process.</p> <p>Researchers will review collected data, and transcripts will be checked against audio recordings. Qualitative analysis will follow a transparent coding framework, with findings discussed and validated through team meetings and member checking.</p>
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation	
IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p><u>How will the data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research process?</u> All data will be stored on a secure, password-protected server of the Medical University of Graz with regular automated backups.</p> <p>For audio recordings of qualitative interviews, recording devices will be used. After data collection, audio recordings will then be transferred by CSs to the university's password-protected Cloud platform and from there to secure server. Original audio files on recording devices will be deleted after transcription.</p> <p><u>How will data security and access control be ensured?</u> Personal data are pseudonymized by the person responsible for data management (Christina Radl-Karimi) and stored in a project folder. Access to identifiable data will be restricted to authorized research team members. Identifiable data (e.g. contact details) and consent forms will be stored separately from anonymized research data. CSs will receive guidance on secure handling and transfer of all project-related documents.</p>
IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation	<p><u>How and when will data be shared?</u> Due to the sensitive nature of qualitative data and CS participation, raw data will not be openly shared. All data used for analysis and dissemination will be pseudonymised or anonymized. The final co-created guiding principles and anonymized results will be made publicly available through scientific publications and reports.</p> <p><u>In which repository will data be made available?</u> Results will be disseminated via open-access journals, institutional and project websites, and scientific conferences. The project will also be registered on <i>Österreich forscht</i>, the Austrian platform for Citizen Science projects. In addition, we will use the Zenodo repository to register the project, and to publish data</p>

	<p>collection protocols, interview guides, and publications. The research resources will receive a DOI via publication on Zenodo and will be referenced in the publication's Data Availability Statement (DAS). We aim to apply open licenses such as CC BY to our publications whenever possible. As this project involves only a small number of Citizen Scientist participants, sufficiently anonymising the raw data is not feasible. For data protection reasons, no raw data will be deposited in a repository at this stage.</p> <p><u>What data will be preserved and how long?</u></p> <p>Identifiable personal data will be deleted at the end of the project unless CSs give written consent to remain contactable for future research activities. Anonymized or pseudonymized meeting protocols, interview transcripts, analysis outputs, project reports, and process evaluation documentation will be stored for 10 years after project completion.</p>
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V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p><u>How will legal issues be managed?</u></p> <p>The Medical University of Graz is the owner of all project data and exercises the right to control access. Authors retain the right to be named and to publish scientific work independently. CSs have the right to be named as co-authors in publications of research results.</p> <p>No third-party data will be reused, and no specific intellectual property rights are expected to arise from the qualitative data</p> <p>The project complies with GDPR and the Medical University of Graz <i>Guidelines on Standards for Good Scientific Practice</i>. Written informed consent will be obtained from all CSs and participants. Personal data will be anonymized or pseudonymized, stored separately, and accessed only by authorized staff. No public access to personal data is planned.</p>
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V.2 Ethical aspects	<p><u>What ethical issues will be taken into account?</u></p> <p>Citizen Science activities involve specific ethical considerations. Researchers and citizen scientists will address issues related to data quality and integrity, data sharing, intellectual property, conflicts of interest, and also issues related to power dynamics and potential exploitation.</p> <p>Within this project, particular attention will be given to regular reflection on roles and expectations, the creation of an inclusive and respectful environment, open discussion of power dynamics, and trust-building measures to support long-term engagement.</p> <p>The CSs participation in the project is voluntary, and they may withdraw at any time and can revoke the processing of their data at any time. Ethics approval is in progress and will be obtained before data collection begins.</p>
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